

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Supplemental Figure 1: As Figure 1 but including all GP outcomes rather than censoring if the patient had an outcome within the 3 months before index date. AKI and diabetes are unchanged from figure 1.

Supplemental Figure 2: As Figure 1, but without using GP as an outcome (only hospitalisations and death certificate records). AKI and diabetes are unchanged from figure 1.

Supplemental Figure 3: As Figure 2, but outcomes recorded in GP records are not censored if the patient had an outcome within the 3 months before index date.

Supplemental Figure 4: As Figure 2, but without using GP as an outcome (only hospitalisations and death certificate records).

Supplemental Table 1: As Table 2, but outcomes recorded in GP records are not censored if the patient had an outcome within the 3 months before index date.

Outcome	Analysis Group	Person Time (x 1,000 person years)	Number of events	Rate (95% CI)
Stroke	Discharged COVID-19	22.3	1300	58.4(55.3-61.7)
	General Population	375.8	3997	10.6(10.3-11.0)
	Discharged Pneumonia	52.5	3224	61.4(59.3-63.5)
DVT	Discharged COVID-19	22.3	587	26.3(24.3-28.5)
	General Population	376.5	1384	3.7(3.5-3.9)
	Discharged Pneumonia	52.7	1355	25.7(24.4-27.1)
PE	Discharged COVID-19	22.1	1652	74.8(71.2-78.4)
	General Population	376.6	1361	3.6(3.4-3.8)
	Discharged Pneumonia	52.3	2900	55.5(53.5-57.5)
Heart Failure	Discharged COVID-19	21.2	5432	255.8(249.1-262.7)
	General Population	370.9	14408	38.8(38.2-39.5)
	Discharged Pneumonia	47.4	19686	415.2(409.4-421.0)
MI	Discharged COVID-19	22.3	707	31.6(29.4-34.1)
	General Population	376.1	2825	7.5(7.2-7.8)
	Discharged Pneumonia	52.6	2307	43.9(42.1-45.7)
AKI	Discharged COVID-19	21.2	4669	220.4(214.2-226.9)
	General Population	372.9	10298	27.6(27.1-28.1)
	Discharged Pneumonia	49.1	12933	263.4(258.9-268.0)
T2DM	Discharged COVID-19	15.2	670	44.1(40.9-47.6)
	General Population	310.9	2763	8.9(8.6-9.2)
	Discharged Pneumonia	37.1	1360	36.6(34.7-38.6)

Supplemental Table 2: As Table 2, but without using GP as an outcome (only hospitalisations and death) certificate records.

Outcome	Analysis Group	Person Time (x 1,000 person years)	Number of events	Rate (95% CI)
Stroke	Discharged COVID-19	22.4	1009	45.1(42.4-48.0)
	General Population	376.2	3238	8.6(8.3-8.9)
	Discharged Pneumonia	52.7	2650	50.3(48.4-52.2)
DVT	Discharged COVID-19	22.4	396	17.7(16.0-19.5)
	General Population	376.8	843	2.2(2.1-2.4)
	Discharged Pneumonia	52.8	964	18.2(17.1-19.4)
PE	Discharged COVID-19	22.3	1137	51.1(48.2-54.2)
	General Population	376.7	1136	3.0(2.8-3.2)
	Discharged Pneumonia	52.6	2103	40.0(38.3-41.7)
Heart Failure	Discharged COVID-19	21.4	4921	230.1(223.8-236.6)
	General Population	372.4	11706	31.4(30.9-32.0)
	Discharged Pneumonia	48.2	17660	366.0(360.7-371.5)
MI	Discharged COVID-19	22.4	533	23.8(21.9-25.9)
	General Population	376.3	2520	6.7(6.4-7.0)
	Discharged Pneumonia	52.8	1853	35.1(33.6-36.8)
AKI	Discharged COVID-19	21.2	4456	209.7(203.6-216.0)
	General Population	373.1	10044	26.9(26.4-27.5)
	Discharged Pneumonia	49.3	12465	252.9(248.5-257.4)
T2DM	Discharged COVID-19	15.2	670	44.1(40.9-47.6)
	General Population	310.9	2763	8.9(8.6-9.2)
	Discharged Pneumonia	37.1	1360	36.6(34.7-38.6)

Supplemental Table 3: As Table 3, but without using GP as an outcome (only hospitalisations and death) certificate records.

Outcome	Comparator	Comparator Person Time	Comparator Number of events	Discharged COVID-19 Person Time	Discharged COVID-19 Number of events	Crude SHR (95% CI)	Age/Sex adjusted SHR (95% CI)	Fully adjusted SHR (95% CI)
Stroke	General Population	376.2	3238	22.4	1009	4.28(3.99-4.59)	4.30(4.01-4.61)	3.02(2.78-3.27)
	Pneumonia	52.7	2650	22.4	1009	0.83(0.77-0.89)	1.05(0.95-1.16)	1.02(0.92-1.14)
DVT	General Population	376.8	843	22.4	396	6.36(5.64-7.16)	6.37(5.65-7.17)	4.42(3.80-5.13)
	Pneumonia	52.8	964	22.4	396	0.89(0.79-1.00)	0.85(0.74-0.98)	0.97(0.84-1.13)
PE	General Population	376.7	1136	22.3	1137	11.35(10.49-12.28)	11.34(10.48-12.27)	7.85(7.10-8.67)
	Pneumonia	52.6	2103	22.3	1137	1.11(1.03-1.19)	1.19(1.09-1.30)	1.20(1.10-1.32)
Heart Failure	General Population	372.4	11706	21.4	4921	5.24(5.07-5.42)	5.43(5.24-5.61)	2.51(2.41-2.62)
	Pneumonia	48.2	17660	21.4	4921	0.57(0.55-0.59)	0.81(0.77-0.84)	0.87(0.83-0.91)
MI	General Population	376.3	2520	22.4	533	2.96(2.70-3.25)	2.95(2.69-3.24)	1.91(1.71-2.12)
	Pneumonia	52.8	1853	22.4	533	0.63(0.57-0.69)	0.85(0.74-0.97)	0.86(0.75-0.98)
AKI	General Population	373.1	10044	21.2	4456	6.11(5.90-6.33)	6.20(5.99-6.43)	3.18(3.04-3.32)
	Pneumonia	49.3	12465	21.2	4456	0.77(0.74-0.79)	0.96(0.91-1.00)	0.99(0.94-1.04)
T2DM	General Population	310.9	2763	15.2	670	4.16(3.82-4.52)	4.20(3.86-4.57)	2.71(2.45-2.99)
	Pneumonia	37.1	1360	15.2	670	1.15(1.05-1.26)	1.46(1.31-1.63)	1.30(1.15-1.47)

Supplemental Table 4: As Table 3, but outcomes recorded in GP records are not censored if the patient had an outcome within the 3 months before index date.

Outcome	Comparator	Comparator Person Time	Comparator Number of events	Discharged COVID-19 Person Time	Discharged COVID-19 Number of events	Crude SHR (95% CI)	Age/Sex adjusted SHR (95% CI)	Fully adjusted SHR (95% CI)
Stroke	General Population	375.8	3997	22.3	1300	4.36(4.10-4.64)	4.38(4.12-4.66)	3.12(2.90-3.35)
	Pneumonia	52.5	3224	22.3	1300	0.87(0.81-0.92)	1.09(1.00-1.19)	1.06(0.97-1.17)
DVT	General Population	376.5	1384	22.3	587	5.58(5.07-6.14)	5.59(5.08-6.15)	4.06(3.60-4.57)
	Pneumonia	52.7	1355	22.3	587	0.93(0.84-1.02)	0.89(0.79-1.00)	1.01(0.89-1.14)
PE	General Population	376.6	1361	22.1	1652	13.20(12.32-14.15)	13.18(12.30-14.12)	8.82(8.09-9.61)
	Pneumonia	52.3	2900	22.1	1652	1.14(1.07-1.21)	1.20(1.11-1.29)	1.18(1.09-1.27)
Heart Failure	General Population	370.9	14408	21.2	5432	4.72(4.57-4.87)	4.88(4.72-5.04)	2.35(2.26-2.45)
	Pneumonia	47.4	19686	21.2	5432	0.56(0.55-0.58)	0.78(0.75-0.82)	0.85(0.81-0.88)
MI	General Population	376.1	2825	22.3	707	3.36(3.10-3.64)	3.34(3.08-3.63)	2.23(2.03-2.46)
	Pneumonia	52.6	2307	22.3	707	0.65(0.60-0.71)	0.87(0.78-0.98)	0.90(0.80-1.01)
AKI	General Population	372.9	10298	21.2	4669	6.20(5.99-6.42)	6.30(6.08-6.52)	3.23(3.09-3.37)
	Pneumonia	49.1	12933	21.2	4669	0.77(0.75-0.80)	0.96(0.92-1.00)	1.00(0.95-1.04)
T2DM	General Population	310.9	2763	15.2	670	4.16(3.82-4.52)	4.20(3.86-4.57)	2.71(2.45-2.99)
	Pneumonia	37.1	1360	15.2	670	1.15(1.05-1.26)	1.46(1.31-1.63)	1.30(1.15-1.47)

Supplemental Table 5: Rates of stroke amongst patients discharged with COVID-19 in 2020, all patients discharged with non-COVID pneumonia in 2019 and a matched (age, sex and region) general population comparator group in 2019

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>Analysis Group</i>	<i>Person Time (x 1,000 person years)</i>	<i>Number of events</i>	<i>Rate (95% CI)</i>
<i>Overall</i>		<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	22.3	1128	50.5(47.7-53.6)
		<i>General Population</i>	375.9	3938	10.5(10.2-10.8)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	52.6	2939	55.8(53.9-57.9)
<i>Age</i>	<i>18-49</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	4.9	46	9.4(7.0-12.5)
		<i>General Population</i>	77.2	52	0.7(0.5-0.9)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	6	86	14.4(11.6-17.8)
<i>50-59</i>		<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	3.8	73	19.1(15.2-24.0)
		<i>General Population</i>	59.4	133	2.2(1.9-2.7)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	5.3	116	22.0(18.3-26.4)
<i>60-69</i>		<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	3.8	134	34.9(29.5-41.3)
		<i>General Population</i>	62.2	286	4.6(4.1-5.2)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	8.4	291	34.6(30.8-38.8)
<i>70-79</i>		<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	4.4	293	66.5(59.3-74.6)
		<i>General Population</i>	76.5	790	10.3(9.6-11.1)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	13.7	735	53.7(50.0-57.7)
<i>80+</i>		<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	5.3	582	108.9(100.4-118.1)

		<i>General Population</i>	100.6	2677	26.6(25.6-27.6)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	19.3	1711	88.8(84.7-93.1)
<i>Sex</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	10.6	489	46.0(42.1-50.3)
		<i>General Population</i>	182.3	1857	10.2(9.7-10.7)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	26.6	1372	51.6(49.0-54.4)
<i>Male</i>		<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	11.7	639	54.7(50.6-59.1)
		<i>General Population</i>	193.6	2081	10.8(10.3-11.2)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	26.1	1567	60.1(57.2-63.2)
<i>Ethnicity</i>	<i>White</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	13.7	776	56.7(52.8-60.8)
		<i>General Population</i>	242.7	2558	10.5(10.1-10.9)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	35.2	1900	54.0(51.6-56.4)
<i>Mixed</i>		<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	0.2	7	30.2(14.4-63.4)
		<i>General Population</i>	2.5	17	6.9(4.3-11.1)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	0.2	16	79.8(48.9-130.2)
<i>Asian / Asian British</i>		<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	2.3	80	34.1(27.4-42.5)
		<i>General Population</i>	19.1	136	7.1(6.0-8.4)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	2	108	52.8(43.7-63.8)
<i>Black</i>		<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	0.8	22	28.7(18.9-43.6)
		<i>General Population</i>	6.6	52	7.9(6.0-10.4)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	0.5	36	70.2(50.7-97.4)

<i>Other</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	0.4	7	17.5(8.4-36.8)
	<i>General Population</i>	4.5	18	4.0(2.5-6.3)
	<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	0.3	13	40.0(23.2-68.8)
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<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	4.9	236	48.3(42.5-54.9)
	<i>General Population</i>	100.4	1157	11.5(10.9-12.2)
	<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	14.3	866	60.4(56.5-64.6)
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Supplemental Table 6: Rates of DVT amongst patients discharged with COVID-19 in 2020, all patients discharged with non-COVID pneumonia in 2019 and a matched (age, sex and region) general population comparator group in 2019

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>Analysis Group</i>	<i>Person Time (x 1,000 person years)</i>	<i>Number of events</i>	<i>Rate (95% CI)</i>
<i>Overall</i>		<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	22.3	529	23.7(21.8-25.8)
		<i>General Population</i>	376.5	1357	3.6(3.4-3.8)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	52.7	1248	23.7(22.4-25.0)
<i>Age</i>	<i>18-49</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	4.9	71	14.5(11.5-18.3)
		<i>General Population</i>	77.2	92	1.2(1.0-1.5)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	6	149	25.0(21.3-29.4)
	<i>50-59</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	3.8	71	18.5(14.7-23.4)
		<i>General Population</i>	59.4	90	1.5(1.2-1.9)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	5.3	122	23.1(19.4-27.6)
	<i>60-69</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	3.8	91	23.7(19.3-29.1)
		<i>General Population</i>	62.3	149	2.4(2.0-2.8)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	8.4	216	25.7(22.5-29.3)
<i>70-79</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	4.4	134	30.4(25.7-36.0)	
	<i>General Population</i>	76.7	298	3.9(3.5-4.3)	
	<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	13.7	303	22.1(19.7-24.7)	
<i>80+</i>		<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	5.4	162	30.2(25.9-35.2)

		<i>General Population</i>	101	728	7.2(6.7-7.8)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	19.4	458	23.7(21.6-25.9)
<i>Sex</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	10.6	254	23.9(21.1-27.0)
		<i>General Population</i>	182.5	710	3.9(3.6-4.2)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	26.6	647	24.3(22.5-26.3)
	<i>Male</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	11.7	275	23.5(20.9-26.5)
		<i>General Population</i>	194	647	3.3(3.1-3.6)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	26.1	601	23.0(21.2-24.9)
<i>Ethnicity</i>	<i>White</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	13.7	362	26.4(23.8-29.3)
		<i>General Population</i>	243.2	930	3.8(3.6-4.1)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	35.3	856	24.3(22.7-26.0)
	<i>Mixed</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	0.2	7	30.5(14.6-64.0)
		<i>General Population</i>	2.5	10	4.1(2.2-7.6)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	0.2	<5	24.6(10.3-59.2)
	<i>Asian / Asian British</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	2.4	25	10.6(7.2-15.7)
		<i>General Population</i>	19.2	31	1.6(1.1-2.3)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	2.1	31	15.1(10.6-21.5)
<i>Black</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	0.8	9	11.7(6.1-22.5)	
	<i>General Population</i>	6.6	25	3.8(2.6-5.6)	
	<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	0.5	18	35.0(22.1-55.6)	

<i>Other</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	0.4	6	15.0(6.8-33.5)
	<i>General Population</i>	4.5	12	2.7(1.5-4.7)
	<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	0.3	6	18.4(8.2-40.9)
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<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	4.9	120	24.6(20.6-29.4)
	<i>General Population</i>	100.6	349	3.5(3.1-3.8)
	<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	14.4	332	23.1(20.8-25.7)
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Supplemental Table 7: Rates of PE amongst patients discharged with COVID-19 in 2020, all patients discharged with non-COVID pneumonia in 2019 and a matched (age, sex and region) general population comparator group in 2019

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>Analysis Group</i>	<i>Person Time (x 1,000 person years)</i>	<i>Number of events</i>	<i>Rate (95% CI)</i>
<i>Overall</i>		<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	22.2	1270	57.2(54.1-60.4)
		<i>General Population</i>	376.6	1327	3.5(3.3-3.7)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	52.5	2316	44.1(42.3-45.9)
<i>Age</i>	<i>18-49</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	4.9	162	33.2(28.5-38.8)
		<i>General Population</i>	77.2	45	0.6(0.4-0.8)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	5.9	230	38.8(34.1-44.1)
	<i>50-59</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	3.8	211	55.6(48.6-63.7)
		<i>General Population</i>	59.4	73	1.2(1.0-1.5)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	5.2	213	40.7(35.5-46.5)
	<i>60-69</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	3.8	261	68.5(60.7-77.3)
		<i>General Population</i>	62.3	172	2.8(2.4-3.2)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	8.4	449	53.7(49.0-58.9)
<i>70-79</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	4.4	288	65.6(58.5-73.7)	
	<i>General Population</i>	76.6	386	5.0(4.6-5.6)	
	<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	13.7	649	47.5(44.0-51.3)	
<i>80+</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	5.4	348	65.0(58.5-72.2)	
	<i>General Population</i>	101.1	651	6.4(6.0-6.9)	

		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	19.3	775	40.1(37.4-43.0)
<i>Sex</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	10.6	537	50.7(46.6-55.2)
		<i>General Population</i>	182.6	661	3.6(3.3-3.9)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	26.5	1218	46.0(43.5-48.7)
	<i>Male</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	11.6	733	63.0(58.6-67.8)
		<i>General Population</i>	194.1	666	3.4(3.2-3.7)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	26	1098	42.2(39.8-44.7)
<i>Ethnicity</i>	<i>White</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	13.6	858	63.0(58.9-67.3)
		<i>General Population</i>	243.2	925	3.8(3.6-4.1)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	35.1	1555	44.3(42.1-46.5)
	<i>Mixed</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	0.2	11	47.7(26.4-86.2)
		<i>General Population</i>	2.5	8	3.3(1.6-6.5)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	0.2	9	44.7(23.2-85.8)
	<i>Asian / Asian British</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	2.3	90	38.5(31.3-47.3)
		<i>General Population</i>	19.2	34	1.8(1.3-2.5)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	2	48	23.4(17.7-31.1)
	<i>Black</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	0.8	35	46.0(33.0-64.1)
		<i>General Population</i>	6.6	10	1.5(0.8-2.8)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	0.5	31	60.8(42.8-86.5)
<i>Other</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	0.4	18	45.5(28.6-72.1)	
	<i>General Population</i>	4.5	6	1.3(0.6-2.9)	

	<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	0.3	8	24.5(12.2-49.0)
<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	4.9	258	53.0(47.0-59.9)
	<i>General Population</i>	100.7	344	3.4(3.1-3.8)
	<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	14.3	665	46.5(43.1-50.2)

Supplemental Table 8: Rates of heart failure amongst patients discharged with COVID-19 in 2020, all patients discharged with non-COVID pneumonia in 2019 and a matched (age, sex and region) general population comparator group in 2019

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>Analysis Group</i>	<i>Person Time (x 1,000 person years)</i>	<i>Number of events</i>	<i>Rate (95% CI)</i>
<i>Overall</i>		<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	21.3	5152	241.7(235.2-248.4)
		<i>General Population</i>	371.1	14123	38.1(37.4-38.7)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	47.9	18566	387.5(381.9-393.1)
<i>Age</i>	<i>18-49</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	4.9	148	30.4(25.9-35.7)
		<i>General Population</i>	77.2	74	1.0(0.8-1.2)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	5.9	329	55.8(50.1-62.2)
	<i>50-59</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	3.8	289	76.8(68.4-86.2)
		<i>General Population</i>	59.3	287	4.8(4.3-5.4)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	5.1	691	136.1(126.3-146.6)
	<i>60-69</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	3.7	580	156.4(144.1-169.6)
		<i>General Population</i>	61.9	818	13.2(12.3-14.1)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	7.8	1970	251.2(240.3-262.5)
<i>70-79</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	4.1	1399	340.1(322.7-358.4)	
	<i>General Population</i>	75.5	2652	35.1(33.8-36.5)	
	<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	12.3	4909	397.7(386.8-409.0)	
<i>80+</i>		<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	4.9	2736	563.4(542.7-584.9)

		<i>General Population</i>	97.1	10292	106.0(103.9-108.0)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	16.8	10667	636.6(624.6-648.8)
<i>Sex</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	10.2	2348	230.8(221.6-240.3)
		<i>General Population</i>	180	6608	36.7(35.8-37.6)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	24.3	8927	368.0(360.4-375.7)
	<i>Male</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	11.1	2804	251.7(242.5-261.1)
		<i>General Population</i>	191.1	7515	39.3(38.5-40.2)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	23.7	9639	407.5(399.4-415.7)
<i>Ethnicity</i>	<i>White</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	13	3505	269.4(260.6-278.5)
		<i>General Population</i>	239.5	9446	39.4(38.7-40.2)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	32.1	12214	380.2(373.5-387.0)
	<i>Mixed</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	0.2	13	57.4(33.3-98.8)
		<i>General Population</i>	2.4	38	15.6(11.3-21.4)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	0.2	67	361.8(284.7-459.6)
	<i>Asian</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	2.3	289	126.3(112.6-141.8)
		<i>General Population</i>	19	515	27.2(24.9-29.6)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	1.8	762	418.9(390.2-449.7)
	<i>Black</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	0.7	80	106.9(85.8-133.1)
		<i>General Population</i>	6.5	150	23.1(19.6-27.1)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	0.5	157	332.1(284.0-388.3)

<i>Other</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	0.4	28	71.5(49.4-103.5)
	<i>General Population</i>	4.5	49	10.8(8.2-14.4)
	<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	0.3	109	366.3(303.6-441.9)
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<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	4.7	1237	265.9(251.5-281.1)
	<i>General Population</i>	99.1	3925	39.6(38.4-40.8)
	<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	13	5257	403.9(393.1-415.0)
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Supplemental Table 9: Rates of MI amongst patients discharged with COVID-19 in 2020, all patients discharged with non-COVID pneumonia in 2019 and a matched (age, sex and region) general population comparator group in 2019

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>Analysis Group</i>	<i>Person Time (x 1,000 person years)</i>	<i>Number of events</i>	<i>Rate (95% CI)</i>
<i>Overall</i>		<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	22.4	593	26.5(24.5-28.7)
		<i>General Population</i>	376.1	2797	7.4(7.2-7.7)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	52.7	1985	37.7(36.0-39.3)
<i>Age</i>	<i>18-49</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	4.9	18	3.7(2.3-5.8)
		<i>General Population</i>	77.2	48	0.6(0.5-0.8)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	6	30	5.0(3.5-7.2)
	<i>50-59</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	3.8	51	13.3(10.1-17.5)
		<i>General Population</i>	59.4	171	2.9(2.5-3.3)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	5.3	105	19.9(16.4-24.0)
	<i>60-69</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	3.8	90	23.4(19.0-28.8)
		<i>General Population</i>	62.2	330	5.3(4.8-5.9)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	8.4	280	33.3(29.6-37.4)
<i>70-79</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	4.4	167	37.8(32.5-44.0)	
	<i>General Population</i>	76.6	595	7.8(7.2-8.4)	
	<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	13.7	543	39.6(36.4-43.1)	
<i>80+</i>		<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	5.4	267	49.8(44.1-56.1)

		<i>General Population</i>	100.8	1653	16.4(15.6-17.2)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	19.3	1027	53.2(50.0-56.5)
<i>Sex</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	10.7	235	22.0(19.4-25.0)
		<i>General Population</i>	182.5	1056	5.8(5.4-6.2)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	26.6	847	31.8(29.8-34.0)
	<i>Male</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	11.7	358	30.6(27.5-33.9)
		<i>General Population</i>	193.7	1741	9.0(8.6-9.4)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	26.1	1138	43.6(41.2-46.2)
<i>Ethnicity</i>	<i>White</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	13.7	373	27.2(24.5-30.1)
		<i>General Population</i>	242.9	1840	7.6(7.2-7.9)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	35.3	1313	37.2(35.3-39.3)
	<i>Mixed</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	0.2	7	30.4(14.5-63.8)
		<i>General Population</i>	2.5	10	4.1(2.2-7.6)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	0.2	<5	9.8(2.5-39.3)
	<i>Asian</i> <i>/ Asian British</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	2.4	48	20.4(15.4-27.1)
		<i>General Population</i>	19.1	162	8.5(7.3-9.9)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	2	126	61.7(51.8-73.5)
	<i>Black</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	0.8	8	10.4(5.2-20.8)
		<i>General Population</i>	6.6	31	4.7(3.3-6.7)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	0.5	13	25.1(14.6-43.2)

<i>Other</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	0.4	6	15.1(6.8-33.6)
	<i>General Population</i>	4.5	16	3.5(2.2-5.8)
	<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	0.3	10	30.6(16.5-56.8)
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<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	4.9	151	30.9(26.3-36.2)
	<i>General Population</i>	100.5	738	7.3(6.8-7.9)
	<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	14.4	521	36.3(33.3-39.5)
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Supplemental Table 10: Rates of AKI amongst patients discharged with COVID-19 in 2020, all patients discharged with non-COVID pneumonia in 2019 and a matched (age, sex and region) general population comparator group in 2019

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>Analysis Group</i>	<i>Person Time (x 1,000 person years)</i>	<i>Number of events</i>	<i>Rate (95% CI)</i>
<i>Overall</i>		<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	21.2	4522	213.0(206.9-219.3)
		<i>General Population</i>	373	10277	27.6(27.0-28.1)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	49.2	12631	256.6(252.1-261.1)
<i>Age</i>	<i>18-49</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	4.8	240	49.9(44.0-56.6)
		<i>General Population</i>	77.1	99	1.3(1.0-1.6)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	5.8	489	84.6(77.4-92.4)
	<i>50-59</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	3.7	348	94.2(84.8-104.6)
		<i>General Population</i>	59.3	242	4.1(3.6-4.6)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	5	689	137.4(127.6-148.1)
	<i>60-69</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	3.6	623	170.8(157.9-184.7)
		<i>General Population</i>	62	628	10.1(9.4-10.9)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	7.9	1526	192.5(183.1-202.4)
<i>70-79</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	4.1	1208	294.4(278.2-311.4)	
	<i>General Population</i>	75.9	1974	26.0(24.9-27.2)	
	<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	12.7	3380	266.1(257.3-275.3)	
<i>80+</i>		<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	5	2103	422.9(405.2-441.4)

		<i>General Population</i>	98.6	7334	74.4(72.7-76.1)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	17.8	6547	367.7(358.9-376.7)
<i>Sex</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	10.2	2012	197.7(189.2-206.5)
		<i>General Population</i>	181	4734	26.2(25.4-26.9)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	25	5865	234.3(228.3-240.3)
	<i>Male</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	11.1	2510	227.1(218.4-236.2)
		<i>General Population</i>	192	5543	28.9(28.1-29.6)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	24.2	6766	279.6(273.1-286.4)
<i>Ethnicity</i>	<i>White</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	13	3049	234.3(226.2-242.8)
		<i>General Population</i>	240.9	6889	28.6(27.9-29.3)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	33.1	8354	252.7(247.4-258.2)
	<i>Mixed</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	0.2	18	79.4(50.0-126.0)
		<i>General Population</i>	2.4	30	12.3(8.6-17.6)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	0.2	44	238.0(177.1-319.8)
	<i>Asian</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	2.3	255	112.8(99.8-127.6)
		<i>General Population</i>	19	355	18.7(16.9-20.8)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	1.8	469	253.6(231.7-277.6)
<i>Black</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	0.7	99	138.1(113.4-168.2)	
	<i>General Population</i>	6.5	146	22.5(19.1-26.5)	
	<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	0.5	130	280.6(236.3-333.2)	

<i>Other</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	0.4	24	61.8(41.4-92.2)
	<i>General Population</i>	4.5	50	11.1(8.4-14.6)
	<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	0.3	72	240.6(191.0-303.1)
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<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	4.6	1077	232.8(219.3-247.2)
	<i>General Population</i>	99.7	2807	28.2(27.1-29.2)
	<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	13.4	3562	266.2(257.6-275.1)
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Supplemental Table 11: Rates of T2DM amongst patients discharged with COVID-19 in 2020, all patients discharged with non-COVID pneumonia in 2019 and a matched (age, sex and region) general population comparator group in 2019

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>Analysis Group</i>	<i>Person Time (x 1,000 person years)</i>	<i>Number of events</i>	<i>Rate (95% CI)</i>
<i>Overall</i>		<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	15.2	670	44.1(40.9-47.6)
		<i>General Population</i>	310.9	2763	8.9(8.6-9.2)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	37.1	1360	36.6(34.7-38.6)
<i>Age</i>	<i>18-49</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	4.1	136	33.2(28.0-39.3)
		<i>General Population</i>	74.1	228	3.1(2.7-3.5)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	5.3	107	20.3(16.8-24.5)
	<i>50-59</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	2.7	138	51.8(43.8-61.2)
		<i>General Population</i>	52.5	379	7.2(6.5-8.0)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	4	127	31.5(26.5-37.5)
	<i>60-69</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	2.3	139	59.2(50.1-69.9)
		<i>General Population</i>	50.7	509	10.0(9.2-10.9)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	5.7	252	44.2(39.0-50.0)
<i>70-79</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	2.7	126	47.5(39.9-56.6)	
	<i>General Population</i>	58.2	698	12.0(11.1-12.9)	
	<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	9	389	43.5(39.3-48.0)	

	80+	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	3.4	131	38.4(32.3-45.5)
		<i>General Population</i>	75.4	949	12.6(11.8-13.4)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	13.2	485	36.8(33.7-40.2)
Sex	Female	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	7.5	300	39.8(35.5-44.5)
		<i>General Population</i>	154.5	1154	7.5(7.1-7.9)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	19.4	643	33.2(30.7-35.8)
	Male	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	7.6	370	48.5(43.8-53.7)
		<i>General Population</i>	156.5	1609	10.3(9.8-10.8)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	17.8	717	40.4(37.5-43.5)
Ethnicity	White	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	9.6	400	41.5(37.7-45.8)
		<i>General Population</i>	202.8	1741	8.6(8.2-9.0)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	25.1	891	35.5(33.2-37.9)
	Mixed	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	0.1		13.5(3.4-53.9)
		<i>General Population</i>	2	17	8.6(5.4-13.9)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	0.1		39.7(16.5-95.5)
	Asian / Asian British	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	1.2	73	58.8(46.7-73.9)
		<i>General Population</i>	12.7	182	14.4(12.4-16.6)
		<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	0.9	60	69.1(53.7-89.0)
Black	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	0.4	29	69.0(47.9-99.2)	
	<i>General Population</i>	4.7	47	10.0(7.6-13.4)	

	<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	0.3	12	41.4(23.5-72.9)
<i>Other</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	0.3	11	42.1(23.3-76.0)
	<i>General Population</i>	3.7	31	8.3(5.8-11.8)
	<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	0.2	7	37.2(17.7-78.0)
<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Discharged COVID-19</i>	3.5	155	44.6(38.1-52.2)
	<i>General Population</i>	85.1	745	8.8(8.1-9.4)
	<i>Discharged Pneumonia</i>	10.5	385	36.5(33.1-40.4)